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Techno-economic assessment of CO₂ capture from oxygen-enriched flue gases using PZ-AMP

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25/05/2026 VTT – beyond the obvious

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Motivation & background

- Oxygen enrichment of combustion air can improve post-combustion CO₂ capture by increasing CO₂ partial pressure and reducing flue gas flow
- Growing interest driven by power-to-X concepts, since water electrolysis produces oxygen as a by-product
- Goal of this study is to quantify the effects of oxygen enrichment to CO₂ capture by techno-economic assessment with rate-based modelling using Aspen Plus

Studied cases from a bio-CHP plant

- Oxygen-enriched combustion cases evaluated are from Stockholm Exergi's biomass fueled 135 MW_e/330 MW_{th} ([NS Energy, 5.3.2026](#)) KVV8 CHP plant ([Rosell, 2025](#))
- Three scenarios are studied for CO₂ capture with piperazine-amino-methyl-propanol (PZ-AMP, CESAR1):
 1. a base case with conventional air combustion (21% of O₂)
 2. a moderate oxygen-enrichment level (26% O₂) that does not require major changes to the power plant, and
 3. a higher oxygen-enrichment level (34% O₂) requiring limited modifications to the plant.
- Compared cases:
 - Capture rate 90% and changing solvent flow rate accordingly
 - Solvent flow rate kept constant and allowing capture rate to increase
- Process and equipment are sized for air combustion flue gas, equal amount of CO₂ to the capture process assumed for all cases (45 kg/s, 162 t/h)

Case	O ₂ content of the combustion air	CO ₂ content of the flue gas	Capture rate	Solvent flow rate
1 air combustion	21 vol-%	17.0 vol-%	90%	?
2A	26 vol-%	21.5 vol-%	90%	?
2B	26 vol-%	21.5 vol-%	?	Same as in base case
3A	34 vol-%	28.3 vol-%	90%	?
3B	34 vol-%	28.3 vol-%	?	Same as in base case

Aspen Plus model & assumptions

- Steady-state Aspen Plus model (v14) by [Morlando et al. \(2025\)](#) was modified to simulate a process for flue gas with higher concentration of CO₂

Column parameter	Absorber	Stripper	Wash column
Calculation type	Rate-based	Rate-based	Rate-based
Packing height	20 m	10 m	4 m
Diameter	10 m	6.3 m	8 m
Stages	30	30	5
Packing type	Flexipac 2Y	Flexipac 2Y	Flexipac 2Y
Reactions	Kinetic	Equilibrium	Kinetic
Intercooling stages	Total liquid leaving at stage 16, returns to above stage 17 (cooled to 40 °C)	-	-
Flooding	74%	73%	71%
Pressure	1 atm	1.8 bar(a)	1 bar(a)
Discretization	5 liquid phase discr. points	5 liquid phase discr. points	5 liquid phase discr. points

Assumption	
Method	ENRTL-RK
Mass transfer coefficient method	Brf-85
Holdup method correlation	Brf-92

Aspen Plus model validation

- Model was validated to the recent results of a pilot plant at Aalborg Portland site in Denmark. The pilot used CESAR1 as solvent while capturing CO₂ from flue gas from cement production

Parameter	Base case results (pilot) ¹	Base case results (model)	Intercooling results (pilot) ¹	Intercooling results (model)
Specific reboiler duty, GJ/t CO ₂	3.4	3.2 (-5.9%)	3.1	3.1
Stripping intensity, kJ/kg _{rich solvent}	261	265 (+1.5%)	279	282 (+1.5%)
CO ₂ concentration into the plant, %	19.2	19.2	17.7	17.7
Rich solvent flow rate, kg/h	300	299 (-0.3%)	280	279 (-0.4%)
Energy to reboiler, kW	22.0	22.0	22.0	21.9 (-0.7%)
Temperature at the top ² of stripper, °C	88	88	92	92
Capture efficiency, %	89	89	98	98
Cyclic load ($\Delta\alpha$) ³ , mol/mol	0.34	0.37 (+8.8%)	0.38	0.41 (+6.6%)

1) [Appelquist Løge et al. 2025](#)

2) Confirmed from the responsible author to be temperature of the top, not the bottom of the stripper

3) Refers to the difference of the loadings (rich loading–lean loading)

- **Model can be used for higher CO₂ concentrations with good accuracy**

Item	Assumption
Oxygen, O ₂	50 €/t
Electricity	60 €/MWh
Steam	15 €/MWh ¹
PZ	4.2 €/kg ²
AMP	2.5 €/kg ²
Annual operating time	7000 h/a
Economic lifetime	20 years
WACC	8%
Fixed operating costs	4% of FCI

1) Estimated as the cost of lost electricity production due to steam bleeding

2) [Lassagne et al. 2016](#)

- CO₂ capture process is sized for the base case (air combustion) with reasonable but not optimized assumptions
- Equipment costing mainly performed using Aspen Process Economic Analyzer

Technical results: capture rate and reboiler energy

- Base case with air combustion has the highest heating need (stripper reboiler energy)
- Oxygen enrichment reduces the reboiler duty → lowest energy need with highest O₂ amount and 90% capture rate
- Using the same amount of solvent as in base case increases capture rate to:
 - 93%** (in moderate, 26% O₂ case)
 - 96%** (in higher, 34% O₂ case)

Economic assessment and results: capture cost

- Base case (air combustion) leads to the lowest capture cost with assumed oxygen price of 50 €/t (when producing O₂ specifically for this purpose)
- With OEC, higher capture rate leads to lower specific capture cost

Estimated Fixed capital investment (FCI): 210 M€

Water costs are not considered, and only electricity needed for the compression of the increased amount of recycled gases is considered (no other effects of increased O₂ amount)

Effect of oxygen price to capture cost

- Savings from reduced energy consumption and improved capture rate are not enough to compensate for the cost of oxygen, except when oxygen price is
 - lower than 1.7-6.1 €/t (for 26% O₂ case) or
 - lower than 1.9-6.6 €/t (for 34% O₂ case)
- Note: not considering the costs of the changes required to the plant (in 34% O₂ case)

Maximum price of the changes to the plant

- Higher oxygen-enrichment level (34% O₂) requires modifications to the plant (in flue gas recirculation system, e.g. compressor), so we looked at how much increase in CAPEX is possible to reach the breakeven price (assuming oxygen is available for free):

	OEC with 34% O ₂ and 90% capture rate	OEC with 34% O ₂ and same solvent amount as in base case
Maximum price of changes, compared to base case	5.3 M€	18.5 M€
Maximum price of changes, compared to 26% case with constant solvent flowrate	-	9.0 M€

- Breakeven oxygen price for 26% and 34% cases (with constant solvent flowrate) is 7 €/t
 - If oxygen would cost 5 €/t, the maximum price of the changes would be 2.7 M€ with constant solvent amount (compared to 26% case)
 - However, oxygen will likely cost a bit more → 26% O₂ case seems more attractive

Conclusions

- With a capture process designed for air combustion, oxygen enriched combustion (OEC) can either
 - reduce the energy need of regeneration (reboiler duty) by 2-5% or
 - allow 3-6% higher capture rate when using PZ-AMP
- Profitability of OEC¹ from the perspective of the PZ-AMP capture process requires almost always oxygen to be almost free
 - Probably Hot potassium carbonate (HPC) process would benefit more from OEC → room for further work
- As oxygen will probably never be free, the moderate oxygen-enrichment level (26% O₂) is probably more attractive even if using side product oxygen from electrolyser

1) Not including the effects of OEC to the power plant (e.g. efficiency, heat and power production)

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Thank you!

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